

Monitoring commercial cloud service providers

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Abstract

There is a growing tendency by individuals to sign-up for public commercially operated cloud services without any involvement from the CERN IT department. The risks from these cloud services include issues around data security, transaction integrity, business continuity and regulatory compliance. This paper reports the most appropriate means to detect and measure usage of the most common commercial cloud services from devices on the CERN site.

The results of the study summarise the scale, frequency and distribution of public commercially operated cloud services from devices on the CERN site.

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Abbreviation	Definition
AS	Within the Internet, an Autonomous System ¹ is a collection of connected Internet Protocol routing prefixes under the control of one or more network operators on behalf of a single administrative entity or domain that presents a common, clearly defined routing policy to the Internet.
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol ² is a standardized exterior gateway protocol designed to exchange routing and reachability information between autonomous systems on the Internet.
DHCP	The Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol ³ is a standardized network protocol used on Internet Protocol networks for dynamically distributing network configuration parameters, such as IP addresses for interfaces and services.
DNS	The Domain Name System ⁴ is a hierarchical distributed naming system for computers, services, or any resource connected to the Internet or a private network.
HTTPS	HTTPS ⁵ is a protocol for secure communication over a computer network which is widely used on the Internet.
IP address	An Internet Protocol address ⁶ is a numerical label assigned to each device (e.g., computer, printer) participating in a computer network that uses the Internet Protocol for communication.
MAC address	A media access control address ⁷ is a unique identifier assigned to network interfaces for

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Autonomous_system_\(Internet\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Autonomous_system_(Internet))

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Border_Gateway_Protocol

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dynamic_Host_Configuration_Protocol

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Domain_Name_System

⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HTTPS>

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IP_address

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MAC_address

	communications on the physical network segment.
NetFlow	NetFlow ⁸ is a feature that provides the ability to collect IP network traffic as it enters or exits an interface.
SNI	Server Name Indication ⁹ is an extension to the TLS computer networking protocol by which a client indicates which hostname it is attempting to connect.
URL	Uniform Resource Locator ¹⁰ is a reference to a resource that specifies the location of the resource on a computer network and a mechanism for retrieving it.
URLgrep	URLgrep is a tool for querying HTTP request history.

⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NetFlow>

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Server_Name_Indication

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uniform_resource_locator

1 Introduction

The threat for using monitoring commercial cloud providers is that confidential documents leak outside of CERN through third party cloud service providers (such as Dropbox, iCloud, OneDrive etc.) without user noticing and understanding it. After the leak, the user has no idea where the data is, who can access it nor what is the availability of the data.

CERN has a lot of alternative in-house services to match commercial products and users are encouraged to use those. The aim of the study is to define how to monitor the traffic and the number of users of cloud service providers and see if they change in a long run.

This study will only cover IPv4 clients as the tool used to get the traffic data does not fully support IPv6 flows and the amount of IPv6 clients is believed to be small.

2 Gathering and analysing the data

The only source of traffic information is NetFlow data which consists of source and destination IP addresses and ports, transport layer protocol, timestamps and the amount of data transferred. This means that IP address ranges and hostname patterns have to be used in order to identify services.

Because majority of cloud services uses encrypted channels (e.g. HTTPS) IP packets cannot be looked inside. This means that DNS queries have to be used in order to measure the number of devices and to which services they are connecting to.

2.1 Gathering the data and identifying services

What comes to identifying different cloud services, a very few of them provide an up-to-date list of their IP address ranges. However, if a service provider has it's own AS number, we can check which networks does it advertise via BGP and use those.

If a service provider doesn't have an AS number and it doesn't provide any IP address range, we have to rely on hostname patterns. Reverse DNS query has to be done for stored NetFlow data and see which name does the IP address resolve to. This method is the last resort as some of the services run inside another cloud provider, like Amazon AWS or EC2, which means that it resolves to Amazon. There are no guarantees that the reverse DNS query will resolve to the same hostname which were queried originally. A good example of this is Google, for example resolving google.com resolves to an IP address but when asking the domain name for the same particular IP address, we will get Googles internal domain (1e100.net). Also not all servers have public DNS records so reverse DNS query may fail.

AS number and networks published via BGP does not purely mean that the results will include only one particular service. For example, Facebook and Instagram traffic come from the same networks and will be interpreted as Facebook traffic.

2.2 NetFlow

“NetFlow is a feature that was introduced on Cisco routers that provides the ability to collect IP network traffic as it enters or exits an interface. By analyzing the data provided by NetFlow, a network administrator can determine things such as the source and destination of traffic, class of service, and the causes of congestion.” [1]

Typical architecture includes exporter, collector and console. Exporter is the source of NetFlow data, usually router but can also be any other device acting as a probe. Collector is a device which collects NetFlow traffic from one or multiple sources. Console acts as a user interface and is used to query the data.

Figure 1: Typical NetFlow architecture¹¹

2.3 DNS

Most of the interesting traffic regarding this study is encrypted (usually HTTPS) which means that we cannot look inside the traffic. As our monitoring tools doesn't support SNI extension, we have to rely on DNS queries in order to identify devices and services they are connecting to. We can query DNS server's logs to find out from which IP address the query was made, to which service and when.

¹¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NetFlow>

2.4 Analysing the data

2.4.1 Traffic and devices

When IP address ranges have been found, queries can be made against them and the results will be saved on disk. Then all the traffic data has to be digested into daily or hourly summaries depending how the data is wanted to be represented. After that the traffic will be divided based on the origin, static and dynamic IP addresses. Then both static and dynamic traffic will be digested into hourly or daily summaries of the traffic. Now we have total traffic, traffic originating from static IP addresses and traffic originating from dynamic IP addresses. In order to calculate the ratio between traffic and devices, the number of users has to be calculated.

When calculating users from DNS log, we have two types of IP addresses: static and dynamic addresses. Static addresses can be calculated as is but a typical mobile device will have multiple different IP addresses during the day. In order to approximate the number of dynamic devices, DHCP log has to be examined in order to compare MAC addresses and IP addresses. A script was written which takes one MAC address at a time and if it has multiple IP addresses in a day, it calculates median of IP addresses per device. The approximation for total number of devices is calculated by adding dynamic devices divided by median to the number of static devices.

2.4.2 URLs

For the services using unencrypted HTTP protocol, URLgrep tool can be used. It reads HTTP requests and this can be used to identify resource creation links, for example URL shortening services or online poll services. This way usage can be identified much more detailed way, not only page visits but what user is actually doing there.

3 Results

This study produced three programs, one for analysing bandwidth usage, one for analysing the number of devices and one for analysing the number of users who use Pastebin, TinyURL and Doodle. The tools support 20 different services and more can be added easily. Bandwidth and device analysers query, analyse and plot results automatically. The URL analyser queries, analyses and prints the results on screen automatically.

As can be seen from the graphs, Dropbox is quite popular with about 1800 devices connecting to it every workday whereas Box.com is not as popular here in CERN. Amazon AWS and Microsoft Azure are not in used much and this can be explained with working in-house alternative (Openstack), but iCloud seems to be as popular with about 2000 devices. Facebook is very popular with about 5000 devices.

Weekend gaps are clearly visible from all the graphs. Something worth to mention are also little usage drops on Monday and Friday which would have been expected to be little peaks rather than drops.

While interpreting devices graphs, approximation bar is the approximation of total number of users. Total bar is for all unique IP addresses, and dynamic and static respectively.

4 Conclusions

The most popular cloud service providers are popular also here in CERN. Market leading cloud service providers are leading in both traffic and the number of devices. Cloud storage service users should be encouraged to use CERNBox as an alternative for all work related things in order to tackle security issues. For all the services one has to understand that not all the traffic is professional usage but also personal usage.

From now on the usage of commercial cloud service providers can be monitored with the three tools written during this project. Query parameters are standardized so results can be compared reliably.

5 Improvements for future

For the future work, it is suggested to implement custom hours for querying, for example from 9:00 to 17:30, and also to enable querying for weekly, monthly and yearly basis.

Trying to improve results by find better hostname patterns for measuring the number of devices and trying to get rid of hostnames once and for all for measuring traffic is important. Only IP address ranges are reliable enough.

Dividing traffic to outgoing and incoming traffic would be interesting for CERNBox team.

Adding support for IPv6 should be prioritized high as CERN network is already fully IPv6 enabled.

Adding more services is easy and should be done when new popular services appear on the market.

After rolling out Bro IDS, it could be beneficial to look into it's passive DNS feature and how that could improve the performance compared to crawling through DNS server logs.

6 Appendix

6.1 Amazon AWS

Amazon AWS does not have bandwidth usage graphs because other services are running inside it so their traffic graphs would include also lots of other services.

6.2 Microsoft Azure

6.3 Box.com

6.4 Dropbox

6.5 Facebook

6.6 Gmail

This graph doesn't show all the users as the query didn't include top level domains (for example gmail.com) but only subdomains.

Gmail does not have graphs as it is impossible to measure traffic reliably based on hostname patterns for this service.

6.7 Hotmail

This graph doesn't show all the users as the query didn't include top level domains but only subdomains.

Hotmail does not have graphs as it is impossible to measure traffic reliably based on hostname patterns for this service.

6.8 iCloud

iCloud does not have graphs as it is impossible to measure traffic reliably based on hostname patterns.

6.9 OneDrive

6.10 Surveymonkey

Surveymonkey does not have much traffic as it is a normal website. So the traffic data is not interesting for this study.